

SHAPING THE ATTITUDE TO THE ENVIRONMENT IN CHILDREN OF THE PREPARATORY GROUP OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract. Preschoolers can be seen in situations that focus on being and adjacent phenomena and love of nature. Special mention is made in the conditions of innovative education of the preservation of all underground and terrestrial resources in nature, the presence of nature in the upbringing of a child and the need to explain its rational use, and by forming their understanding of nature in the conditions of innovative education in older children, they provide information about the importance of raising moral qualities.

Keywords: children, preschool educational organization, innovative environment nature, environmental value, environmental knowledge, love of nature, man, role, conservation, thought, history, introduction, method, science, Red Book, elegance.

Introduction. The part of nature that connects closely with society, affecting its development to some extent, is called the environment. Aesthetic, mental, moral education, physical development through the introduction of the pre-school preparatory group Bo into nature in an innovative environment were considered extremely urgent problems even in all times. In the methodological science of introducing nature, a great place is given to teaching children even through methods of Environmental Education, a summary of the "Red Book" using existing innovations and videos about unique flora and fauna, which are included in the "Red Book".

The main tasks of the methodology of acquaintance with nature should be as follows:

- Teaching children to love their country.
- To train the hard work of oneself, peers and adults.
- Development of psychic processes through nature (sensations, perception, memory, imagination, imagination, speech attention).
- To develop the will of children's hysteria.
- To teach the awe-inspiring preservation of the gifts of nature.

Based on the above tasks, it is necessary to educate children in an all – inclusive environment through nature - mental education; - moral education; - elegance education; - physical education; - environmental education; economic education.

Pouring requirements for the angle of inertial nature:

1. A plant or animal should be specific for any anik, species, and it is necessary that each of them be a piece of paper with information about the named ozi.

2. Those who live in the corner of nature, the "beor" should be a child's age-appropriate Bull, who does not require a lot of work, does not choose food.

3. It is necessary that those who live in the corner of nature become bright, attractive, able to attract the attention of children to the face.

4. Plants and animals of one species should be divided in several ways.

5. Those who live in the corner of nature are absolutely safe and must not cause any harm to the health of children.

6. The number of plants and animals living in the corner of nature is limited, and their biological characteristics must be placed in order.

Acquaintance with nature is a process that conveys a person to spiritual perfection, which prevents him from all negative mistakes leads to perfection. As a result, his love for nature increases with his unruly beauty. For this reason, the educational process by introducing it to nature is considered to have a very long history. In this regard, the peoples of **Central Asia** have a rich tradition in the field of conservation.

In the teachings that preserving nature is a human duty to treat the blessings in it extensively, Turoni is embodied in the teachings of great scientists who have matured from Turkestan. Scientists have recorded rich accounts of the use of nature in their time, the event associated with them, phenomena. They stated in their work that nature should be nurtured with love and high morality.

Of the medieval scholars living in Middle Asia Mukhammad Musa al-Khwarazmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruniy, Abu Ali Ibn Sino and others made outstanding contributions to the development of Natural Science. They made valuable remarks about nature and the balance in it, the flora and fauna, and the veneration of nature in a time when the science of Ecology was not yet in the world. It is such that Muhammad Musa al-Khwarazmiy of our great alms zabardast, who wrote his "Kitab surat al - arz "with Abu Nasr Farabi (870-810)" al - volami and al - mikdor", "Kitab almabodi al - Insan "with Abu Rayhan Beruni's" Saydana", " mineralogy "with Abu Ali ibn Sina, he wrote" Kitab al - healing", " Taz ul - manzil".

He also familiarized himself with his articles on nature, protection of nature, careful treatment of the natural resources of his blessings and care in our Hadith Sharif. it is studied by an in-depth analysis.

Science, Enlightenment - culture has been an indelible torch in the human world for centuries. Our values, unique manuscript works, ancient monuments lying on the rocks of history, unknown to us, are thoroughly studied by our research scientists. History is the path of perfection, progress of a person. Not knowing Moses is not self-awareness. Only a ring of self-realization will always memorize the purity of its spirit, honoring the names of great men. If we look at our past history, our educators, who lived and worked, have argued that in the all-round growth of the child in the periods of their creativity, the subtleties of nature, which give spiritual nourishment, are His wonders. The importance of nature in the upbringing of children of great educators, who left their indelible, memorable name in the jewels of history. those who have mentioned his scientific opinions on how it affects the psyche of a child. In the study of this topic, we asked Western educators: Y.A.Komensky, J.J.Russo, I.G.We will get acquainted with the scientific works of scientists such as Pestolotsii about the role of nature in the upbringing of children.

From Russian educators K.D.We get acquainted with the work of ushinsky, "man as a subject of upbringing".

Ushinsky said " even if you consider me VAR in pedagogy, but I came to this conclusion in my life experience. Beautiful nature has such a great educational influence on the young soul that even the influence of pedagogy is too weak to compete with it."

As we know, a child comes into the world from an early age and communicates with nature. We now rely on the wise thoughts and scientific works of our educators from the past that we use in our pedagogical activities.

The importance of introducing children to nature. Love for nature is a very comprehensive and complex feeling. It forms a complex whole, which includes high spiritual and mental layers. M., who carried out research work on the formation of a responsible attitude to environment in preschool children. Umarova believes that it is of important pedagogical importance to start raising this feeling from an early age in childhood. Each child grows a passion for loving, indulging in the nature of the local land and Uzbekistan, where he lives. This feeling, born in childhood, develops and becomes rich in educational age until school. That's why P.Yusupova in her research work "Formirovaniye nachal materialisticheskogo miroponimania u starshix doshkolnikov v procse oznakomleniya ix s rasteniyami v usloviyax Uzbekistana " Methodist scholar A.V. Zaporozhets gives the following point of view as appropriate: "... preschool age didactics should be established in such a way that children not only do they know the external aspects of the surrounding items, but also get acquainted with the simplest ties between them, the closest causes of the observed phenomena, some features in their changes and developments, such material will not only fit the level, but also be interesting for a preschool child". The child learns the laws of nature by realizing these connections. From the above points, it can be said that introducing children of preschool age to nature in an innovative environment is an educational tool for educating a full - fledged attitude to nature in them and understanding real knowledge of the environment, based on emotional experience.

Observations confirm that the activities of children in the environment are mainly spontaneous, unexpected, and it will be more correct to consider this as the main reason for such an attitude towards nature in their family, neighborhood, in a word, such activities are corrected by the pedagogical influence of those in surroundings, especially educators of a preschool educational institution. That is why it is so important that children as early as preschool age acquire convincing information about nature. In order for children to perceive natural phenomena in full, it is necessary that they be guided by morning walks and afternoon walks. The task of educating children of preschool age in all aspects-mental, aesthetic, moral, physical - cannot be solved in a timely manner, without introducing children to nature and using it extensively in educational work in a preschool educational institution.

Educational and educational tasks of introducing children to nature in an innovative environment.

In the process of introducing children to nature according to the concept of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, interrelated educational and educational tasks are carried out. Its main task in mental education is to provide information about the non - living Nature, Plants, Animals in children, to allow them to adequately perceive the phenomena of nature.

An integral part of mental education is sensory culture. It concerns the improvement of analyzers, strengthening the emotional experience that will become the basis for further generalizations in children, Natural Science. focused on the formation of initial concepts.

Children's acquisition of knowledge of nature in an inpatient environment must be firmly connected with their cognitive abilities - such as sensory apparatus, logical thinking, attention, speech, observability, interest in knowledge. In order to develop thinking and form a scientific worldview, it is necessary to introduce children to nature things-phenomena during walks, teach

them to understand what is being observed-phenomena, and bring them to the realization of communication and relationships between them. Causal connections and relationships between natural phenomena in the process of perception develop thinking.

The child perceives the surrounding environment and certain properties of nature: the hot-coldness of the air during a walk with his skin, the taste of liquids with his tongue, the smell in the air with his nose, the color of various objects in nature with his eyes, the sounds with his ear, that is, these properties affect the child's five different senses, , landscapes come into being.

In children, it is also important to educate an interest in knowledge in an innovative environment. By showing children how to observe animals and plants in a hiking phage, focusing their attention on their appearance, movement, the educator forms in them not only knowledge of nature, but also a responsible attitude towards them. It is only necessary to always take into account the age of the child and know what to focus his attention on this thing and phenomenon. In the process of introducing children to nature, it is necessary to carry out moral, physical, labor and aesthetic education. In the moral development of a child in a loving environment, the main place in him is occupied by love for Mother Nature and careful attitude towards our natural blessings. The closest way to children in this regard is where they grow. When animals and plants are present in the preschool, the children observe them and give them food out of affection, helping the educator. As a result, a careful attitude to nature, love of Labor and habituation to work, responsibility for the assigned work are formed in them on their own.

In order to educate children about hard work, careful attitude to nature, it is necessary to teach them simple ways to water plants and feed animals. Most importantly, it is necessary to achieve self-confidence in children to rejoice in the process and results of the work they are doing. To form the quality of hard work, it is necessary to educate children in respect for their activities by introducing them to the work of adults in nature. Nature is one of the main means of aesthetic and mental education of children. Beauties in nature do not remain without self-indulgence even children of the smallest age. In the process of knowing them about nature, it is necessary to focus their attention on the noise of gardens, bird walks, rustling of leaves, shape and color, smells of flowers, animal movements. An important aspect of this is to create conditions for the child to be able to perceive in his future life the homogeneous beauties of the world.

Requirements for the educator in the process of introducing nature in an innovative environment.

The first thing that happens in nature before the educators of the preschool educational institution is to be able to collect the necessary electronic information about the exchange of seasons of events and make them available to children in an interesting way with various multimedia tools. In order to introduce children to nature in an inhospitable environment using the information collected, it is required to have large reserves of knowledge in various fields of science about nature, understand their developmental laws, correctly assess the possibilities of the field of mind (Noosphere), to be able to isolate the connections between phenomena-something that happens in nature. It is especially important that the nature of the place in which he lives: he is able to observe the alternations of seasons, make a calendar of nature, get used to the skill of breeding plants and flowers.

In children, the upbringing of an active and careful attitude to nature in an inhospitable environment helps to feed animals and plants that are present in a preschool educational institution. The educator is required to be able to organize a living corner of nature, to create conditions for

plants and animals close to their survival in nature. In addition, he should be able to master the agrotechnical methods of watering plants and feeding animals on the corner of the playground and nature of a preschool educational institution in an innovative environment.

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